

TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This project deeply analyzes how traditional knowledge contributes in sustainable development, focusing on two examples – stepwell for conservation of water and fishing ban during monsoon to restore marine ecosystem.

Stepwell system of water conservation ensures water supply throughout the year in arid and semi-arid regions. These systems of water conservation are collective effort of local people for centuries ensuring efficient collection, storage and conservation of water during dry seasons.

Fishing ban is a very common practice observed in the 7500 km long coastal region of our country to restore marine ecosystem. The fisher communities follow these practices for centuries. Approximately 2 – 2.5% of Indian population is dependent on fishing for their livelihood.

Key words: *Traditional Knowledge (TK), Sustainable Development, Non-renewable Resources, Climate Change, Global Warming, Indigenous Wisdom, Natural Resource Utilization, Eco-friendly Practices and Biodiversity Conservation.*

Introduction:

In view of climate change and global warming, everyone's attention is turning towards traditional knowledge for sustainable development.

Ancient people were great observers; they tried to understand the rhythm and the language of nature for efficient and effective use of resources for sustainability.

Traditional knowledge is merely technology-driven; for some people, it might be obsolete; but its relevance can not be denied in current climatic condition.

Post-industrialization development has changed the global infrastructure, economy, and living standard of people in a sustainable way. Now, human mind is dived into the advances of artificial intelligence and it can be used for exploration of other celestial bodies and lives.

Human achievements are commendable, but, depleting potable water, shrinking forest, increasing CO₂ level, irregular pattern of seasons telling another tale. The recent growth and development have created a conspicuous change in the climate. If this situation continues, anthropogenic disaster would be inevitable which might create an uncertainty to the future generation.

Right move at right time is adaptation of traditional knowledge. Still in many parts of our country and world, traditional knowledge is used for renewal of the natural resources. Examples; water conservation in Rajasthan by stepwells through unique architectural design, no fishing during raining season in coastal regions of India, rotational farming, etc.

Literature review:

Journal of Engineering Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR): Features articles like "Stepwell conservation and Adaptive reuse of Step well" by Karishma Mungona and Mrs. Kalpana R. Thakre; April 2025 which explore the historical significance and modern potential of stepwells in states like Rajasthan, Gujarat, and Madhya Pradesh

Stepwells as Heritage Sites: Exploring Their Roles for Sustainable Communities; Kirti Nishant Nikam Department of Sustainable Design, Manipal School of Architecture & Planning, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka; 30 June 2024

According to Press Information Bureau; June 2022; Jalmandirs are stepwells, also known as Baoris, are centuries old architecture for water storage and conservation. They showcase our country's traditional knowledge and cultural ties with water.

Earth Journalism Network (22 November 2021): India imposes a fishing ban every year to allow fish to breed and repopulate the waters, while providing support to fishers.

Press Information Bureau, Government of India, Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare (11 May 2015): Fishing ban is imposed during the monsoon-season, and as the sea becomes turbulent, the fishing ban is necessary to protect life of the fishermen.

Mumbai Magic (19 July 2014): Traditionally the Kolis have a self-imposed ban on fishing in the monsoons; they stop when the rains make the waters too dangerous and rough, and they commence fishing again on Narli Purnima after offering prayers and a coconut (this year Narli Purnima falls on Aug 10).

These studies suggest that fishing ban affects both the **ecological balance** and **socio-economic conditions** of coastal populations.

Objectives:

The primary objective of stepwell design to ensure year-round availability of water even in dry season.

The depth of stepwells helps in replenishing groundwater and their complex structure, site and shape prevent evaporation and heat

Architecture of stepwells helps in understanding the historical and cultural heritage

The fishing ban helps in restoration of marine ecosystem- the ban helps in preservation of the sea environment, aquatic organisms, and factors essential for maintaining the marine life.

Most of the fishes breed during monsoon. Fishing ban enables fishes' availability which is the major resources for the fisher community for their livelihood.

Fishing ban during rainy season safeguards the fishers as sea become rough and fishes go deep into water; this would be dangerous for the fishers.

Methodologies:

Stepwells strategies:

Articles: design, description, location and photographs give description of the ancient technology.

Data collection: from the various sources (Ancient Asia), historical account (exist since 1000 BCE), mentioned in Vedic texts.

Revival efforts - Jalmandir Yojna; Gujarat (2007 – 2012), Delhi stepwells restoration (2014 – 5 medieval stepwells desilted and revived successfully).

Fishing Ban:

Data sources from CMFRI, FAO, Ministry of Fisheries, and state fisheries

Article- Protection for Small-Scale Fisheries in India: A study of India's Monsoon Fishing Ban – Surathal Gunakar, Adam Jadhav and Ramachandra Bhatta

International Journal of Environmental Sciences- Evaluating the Effectiveness and Awareness of Fishing Ban Welfare Schemes In Nagapattinam District, Tamil Nadu -Agash G, Saravanakumar P.

Findings:

Stepwells were designed to store and conserve water, ensuring availability during the dry season.

Their **multi-storied** construction helped reduce evaporation and prevented contamination of stored water.

The deep architecture of stepwells also played a vital role in recharging groundwater.

Beyond their utility, stepwells were often built with artistic and architectural beauty, serving as spaces for religious or social gatherings.

Today, restoration efforts have revived many of these historic structures, making them not only cultural heritage sites but also valuable tools for water conservation in the face of current climatic challenges.

Economic Impact: Economic strain to fishermen for short term who lack alternative. People temporarily shift to other jobs like salt pan work, summer shop employment, etc. The relief amount from the state and the central government disbursed to meet household needs of respondents.

Environment Impact: Fish populations show signs of improvement, particularly in terms of body size and community stability, species diversity. Recovering of spawning ground and marine biodiversity. Restoration of fishery resources.

Policy and Enforcement: Fishing ban varies across states; for instance, **Maharashtra** observes a 61-daysban while **West Bengal** enforces different timelines for mechanized and traditional vessels.

Both state and central Government provide relief fund for the lean period. Pradhan mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana (PMMSY) and Fisheries and Aquaculture Infrastructure Development

Fund (FIDF) provide support and financial assistance for long-term investment in fisheries infrastructures

Social Dimensions: Fisherwomen are engaged in land-based like selling fishes, net mending, sorting, etc. They face income crisis during the ban period. Fishermen communities get engaged in alternative employment (like repair of nets, aquaculture, and tourism) provides partial relief.

Policy implication:

In India, 2800 documented step wells are there. Government and local administration should take initiative to revive stepwells for efficient water management in rural and urban areas.

The ancient architecture could help in recharge of ground water.

Government and non-governmental organisation should initiate **Community awareness programs** should highlight the heritage and ecological importance of such structures.

Restoration and maintenance of historical stepwells should be awarded.

Implementing the Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana (PMMSY) for the welfare of the fishermen. Insurance coverage for fishers

Livelihood and nutritional support for socio-economically backward active traditional fishers' families during fishing ban/lean period.

Encourage Timeliness of Disbursement of relief fund

Introduce Skill Development and Alternative Livelihood Programs: such as mariculture, seaweed farming, and eco-tourism.

Integrating the scheme into a digital platform or mobile application can improve transparency and track the status of applications and payments.

Conclusion:

Traditional methods of water conservation such as stepwells are based on the geology and the climatic condition of a particular region. They remain one of the oldest and most widely used water management techniques in India. (World Bank). The integration of stepwell-based strategies and modern-day technology can significantly help in tackling the water shortage for house hold and agriculture. Their preservation not only conserves water but also safeguards India's cultural heritage for future generations.

A fishing ban during the rainy season allows the marine ecosystem to recover. During this period, fish move into deeper waters and get sufficient time to breed and grow, which helps replenish fish stocks—an essential factor for the long-term sustainability of human beings.

However, such periodic bans do affect the livelihood of local fishing communities. To address this, both state and central governments have introduced various schemes to support fishermen during the lean season. In addition, fishermen can take up short-term alternative jobs or plan their finances wisely during the active fishing season, so that they are better prepared to overcome the challenges of the ban period.

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